

Understanding the Catalytic Activity of N-doped Mesoporous Carbon on the Atomic Level by ^{15}N Solid-State NMR for Electrochemical Denitrification and Oxidative Dehydrogenation of Ethylbenzene

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ABSTRACT: Spherical mesoporous carbon (with a particle size in the range of 40–75 μm) was synthesized by nanoreplication of a hard silica template using sucrose as the carbon precursor. The mesoporous carbon with BET surface areas higher than 1200 m^2/g was doped with N by a treatment in an aqueous solution of nitric acid and/or in a flow of gaseous ammonia. The highest N content (3.2 wt% of N in bulk) was obtained when both modification methods were combined. Complementary physicochemical characterization techniques, including scanning electron microscopy (SEM), low-temperature N_2 adsorption, powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Raman spectroscopy revealed the morphology, structure and textural properties of the synthesized N-loaded carbon materials. For the identification of the detailed chemical structure on the surface of the carbons, ^1H , ^{13}C , and ^{15}N solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) measurements were performed and the data were supported by chemical shift calculations with accurate quantum chemistry methods, and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopic (XPS) analyzes. All NMR experiments were performed at natural isotope abundance. The verified experimental data clearly showed that after the introduction of the N-containing moieties by the combined methods of treatment, a high concentration of pyridinic N at the edge and pyrrolic N being external to the edge was achieved for the mesoporous carbon. The distributed N surface species promoted the catalytic activity in the oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene to styrene, but did not significantly influence the efficiency of the carbon materials in the electrochemical reduction of nitrate ions.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon-based materials have been implemented in a wide range of applications (such as adsorption,^{1,2} electrochemistry^{3–9} and catalysis^{10–12}) for a long time due to their specific properties including structure, porosity, surface composition, and conductivity. In catalytic processes, activated carbons still play a dominant role as the active phase and/or support, while graphene, graphene oxide and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have gained increasingly large interest in the research community.^{3,13–15} In the late 1990s Ryoo et al.¹⁶ developed a new approach for a formation of carbons with a well-controlled mesoporosity. Such materials are produced as negative replicas of silica-type hard templates. After infiltrating a carbon precursor (e.g. sucrose) in a 3D porous system of a SiO_2 matrix, the resulting composite is carbonized and treated with a NaOH or HF solution to remove the inorganic template. Depending on the pore size and wall

arrangement in the silica matrix, carbon materials with various pore architecture are obtained.^{6,17–19}

Doping of carbon with other non-metals results in the formation of different organic functionalities containing most often oxygen,^{15,18–21} nitrogen^{3,8,20,22–24} or sulfur.^{25,26}

The incorporation of heteroatoms into the carbon structure is based on two possible strategies: (i) decomposition of a carbon precursor (e.g. composite, polymer) containing non-metal atoms (bottom-up approach),^{10,17} or (ii) post-synthetic activation of a carbon material using a heteroatom-containing modifier (top-down approach).^{27,28}

Development of various, optimal pathways for the modification with non-carbon species as well as properties of the doped materials is the subject of an increasing number of studies, because the formed functional groups are vital in a variety of applications. Metal-free carbon materials can be considered as green catalysts with respect to their ease of recycling and work efficiently in some catalytic processes, such as oxidative dehydrogenation

of alkanes,^{15,17,24,29,30} where oxygen-containing species located at the edges of graphitic plates are commonly considered to be active sites in an oxidative atmosphere.^{19,21,31} On the other hand, some nitrogen-containing groups, for example pyridinic ones, show activity in acid-base catalysis,¹³ oxygen reduction reactions (ORR)^{3-5,7,8} as well as other electro-transfer processes.^{25,32} Nevertheless, a controlled distribution of heteroatom-containing groups in mesoporous carbon materials remains a big challenge, as their form and stability strongly depends on the temperature, the nature of the heteroatoms as well as the state of the starting carbon material even when model substrates (e.g. graphene, graphene oxides) are used.^{22,33} Combining more than one heteroatom can create heterogeneous groups (like amides) and also induce interactions between surface groups that influence the electrophilicity and electron transfer on the surface of the catalyst.^{17,28} It has been observed that by introducing various amounts of N- and O-containing species, the basicity is influenced, which in turn could be important for the CO₂ adsorption.³⁴ Seo et al.³³ studied a doped reduced graphene oxide material with an optical band gap of 1.7-2.1 eV with implicatively stable N (pyridinic) and O (C=O) surroundings. Electronic synergy also concerns adsorbed molecules, therefore charge generated during the ORR process might be channeled efficiently.^{24,33} Similar interactions occur in the case of other non-metal pairs such as nitrogen doped with phosphorus^{20,35} or boron.³⁶ In addition, with oxygen atoms being connected to high-oxidation-state atoms the deactivation of the active site has been shown to be prevented by Ternero-Hidalgo et al.³⁵

In this work, we discuss the impact of oxygen- and nitrogen-containing groups on the surface of sucrose-derived mesoporous carbon replicas on the performance in the electrochemical nitrate reduction, and the oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene. We propose two approaches to generate heteroatom-containing groups based on treating the replica with (i) a HNO₃ solution, and/or (ii) gaseous NH₃. Especially interesting, original results are obtained by combining the above-mentioned ways, which lead to the formation of nitro moieties (after soaking in the HNO₃ solution) and their subsequent reduction in NH₃ at an elevated temperature. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and ¹⁵N solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (¹⁵N NMR) are used to describe the chemical state of the modified carbon surfaces, and to conclude how these modifications influence the catalytic and electrochemical activity. The use of the ¹⁵N solid-state NMR without isotopic labelling is very promising for further studies as costly ¹⁵N isotope labeling can be circumvented.^{37,38}

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Synthesis. Spherical silica gel (40–75 μm particle size, Supelco) and an acidified sucrose solution (with the H₂O/sugar/H₂SO₄ mass ratio of 50.0/12.5/1.4) were used in the synthesis of the starting carbon replica as a carbon source and a template, respectively. Precisely, 1.0 g of SiO₂ (dried initially at 120 °C for 1 h) was impregnated using the incipient wetness technique with the solution volume containing 1.7 g of sucrose. The obtained composite was placed in an oven at 100 °C for 6 h, then the

temperature was raised to 160 °C for another 6 h. The procedure of impregnation and heating was repeated using the same sucrose solution, 1.6 g of sucrose per 1.0 g of the sample. The material was carbonized in a tubular furnace under a N₂ flow (40 cm³/min) at 650 °C with a heating rate of 1 °C/min and an isothermal period of 4 h. Finally, the silica template was removed by double washing with a HF solution (5 wt.%, room temperature). The produced carbon replica with a negligible amount of the remaining SiO₂ template below 1 wt% (denoted as S0) was isolated, washed with distilled water, ethanol (96%) and dried overnight (50 °C).

A part of the S0 sample was oxidized by a contact with an aqueous solution of HNO₃ (40 wt.%), 1.0 g of S0 per 10 cm³ of the HNO₃ solution at 50 °C for 3 h. The resulting product (denoted as SK) was filtered, washed with distilled water until neutral pH and dried overnight at 50 °C.

Both S0 and SK were modified in the presence of gaseous NH₃ at an elevated temperature. An amount of 100 mg of the sample was placed on a quartz wool plug in a quartz flow microreactor. The material was pre-treated under a N₂ atmosphere (50 cm³/min) at 250 °C for 30 min. Then, temperature raised to 500 °C and the N₂ flow was changed to a NH₃/He mixture (20 vol% of NH₃, total flow rate = 30 cm³/min). The modification lasting for 1 h resulted in obtaining the samples marked S0_N and SK_N, respectively.

N₂ adsorption. N₂ adsorption measurements were performed for outgassed samples (dynamic vacuum, 250 °C, 4 h) at -196 °C in an ASAP 2020 instrument (Micrometrics). The obtained data were analyzed using the following models: Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (specific surface area, S_{BET}), t-plot (micropore volume, V_{micro}), Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (mesopore volume, V_{meso}) and single point at p/p₀ ~ 0.99 (total pore volume, V_{total}).

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD). XRD patterns were collected using Cu K_α radiation (1.54184 Å) with a Bruker D2 Phaser diffractometer equipped with a LYNXEYE detector within a 2θ range of 10–60° using a step of 0.02°.

Raman spectroscopy. Raman spectra were recorded on a LabRAM HR 800 spectrometer equipped with an 800 nm focal length spectrograph. A back thinned CCD detector with 1024×256 pixels and a spectral range of 200-1050 nm was an air cooled at -70 °C. An air cooled double frequency Nd:YAG laser (532 nm/50 mW), edge and interference filters for measurements < 100 cm⁻¹ were used. The laser intensity was adjusted by a software controlled filter wheel with 6ND filters.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM). SEM images were taken on a HITACHI S-4700 field emission microscope at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV. Samples were prepared by mounting powder onto a conducting adhesive carbon disc. In order to reduce charge, the materials were coated with an Au layer.

Elemental analysis. The chemical composition of the carbon materials (content of C, N and H) were determined in a FLASH 2000 elemental analyzer (Thermo Scientific) being equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD), and an autosampler.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. XPS measurements were performed in a Prevac photoelectron spec-

trometer equipped with a hemispherical analyzer (VG SCIENTA R3000). The spectra were taken using a monochromatized aluminum source Al K α (E = 1486.6 eV). The base pressure in the analytical chamber was 5 · 10⁻⁹ mbar. The binding energy scale was calibrated using the Au 4f reference peak at 84.0 eV. The surface composition was analyzed taking into account the areas and binding energies of C 1s, O 1s and N 1s core levels. The spectra were fitted and deconvoluted using the CasaxPS software.

Solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance. All magic-angle-spinning (MAS) NMR experiments were performed at a magnetic field of 14.1 T (Larmor frequencies of 600.12, 150.92, and 60.83 MHz for ¹H, ¹³C, and ¹⁵N, respectively) on a Bruker Avance-III spectrometer. ¹H MAS and ¹H-¹³C heteronuclear correlation (HETCOR) NMR spectra were recorded with a 1.3 mm probehead and 60 kHz MAS rate. Proton acquisitions involved a rotor-synchronized, double-adiabatic spin-echo sequence with a 90° excitation pulse of 1.25 μs followed by a pair of 50.0 μs tanh/tan short high-power adiabatic pulses (SHAPs) with 5 MHz frequency sweep.^{39,40} All pulses operated at the nutation frequency of 200 kHz. 128 signal transients with 1 s relaxation delay were collected. The ¹H-¹³C HETCOR experiment involved Hartmann-Hahn matched ¹H and ¹³C radio frequency fields of 20 and 40 kHz, respectively, 1 ms contact interval for cross-polarization step, 80 kHz SPINAL-64 ¹H decoupling, and 5616 scans with a 1 s relaxation delay collected for each *t*₁ point. The ¹H and ¹³C chemical shifts were referenced with respect to tetramethylsilane (TMS). Directly-excited ¹³C and ¹⁵N MAS NMR spectra were recorded with the single-pulse (“Bloch-decay”) protocol using a 7 mm probehead and 7 kHz MAS rate. The ¹³C and ¹⁵N acquisitions involved 4.0 and 6.0 μs excitation pulses with the nutation frequencies of 63 and 38 kHz, and 9216 and 466944 signal transients collected with recycle delays of 25 s and 1 s respectively. The ¹⁵N NMR chemical shifts are reported with respect to nitromethane. All NMR experiments were performed at natural isotope abundance.

Chemical shifts calculations. All calculations were performed with the ORCA code version 4.1.2.⁴¹ using a tight convergence tolerance of 1x10⁻⁸ Hartree. Models of different nitrogen moieties in the carbon structure were obtained by geometry optimization with dispersion-corrected DFT at the level of the OLYP-D3(BJ) approximation⁴²⁻⁴⁵ using a segmented, polarization consistent pc-2 basis set.⁴⁶ ¹³C and ¹⁵N nuclear shieldings were calculated at the level of perturbatively-corrected DFT with the DSD-PBEP86 approximation⁴⁷ and a segmented pcS-2 basis set⁴⁸ with all electrons included in correlation (no frozen core). The GIAO approach with the RIJCOSX approximation was employed using Coulomb-fitting def2/J⁴⁹ and cc-pwCVTZ/C⁵⁰ auxiliary basis sets for the SCF and MP2 steps respectively, and accurate grid settings for exchange integrals tested. Calculated ¹³C and ¹⁵N nuclear shieldings were converted to ¹³C and ¹⁵N NMR chemical shifts using CO₂ and N₂ molecules in the gas phase as secondary references at 125.0 and -75.3 ppm respectively.^{51,52}

Electrochemical measurements. For preparation of electrodes, a mixture of N-doped carbon and Nafion (D-520 dispersion 5 % w/w in water and 1-propanol, Alfa Aesar) was deposited on a surface of carbon fibre sup-

port (Quintech TP-030). A precursor solution was prepared by dissolving N-doped carbon (5 mg) in 30 μL Nafion and 970 μL ethanol (≥ 99 %, VWR Chemicals). The mixture was dispersed by an Ultrasonic Cleaner (USC 300T, VWR) for 3 min. Then, 200 μL of the uniform mixture was dropped on each side of carbon substrate and dried at room temperature for 1 h. For the preparation of the electrolyte for electrochemical nitrate reduction, NaNO₃ (≥ 99.0 %, Sigma-Aldrich) and Na₂SO₄ (99.0–100.5 wt %, Honeywell Fluka) were dissolved in water purified with a Milli-Q system (18.3 MΩ cm). A platinum wire and a 1 M Ag/AgCl electrode were used as a counter and reference electrode, respectively. The concentration of nitrate was analyzed by the procedure described by Robarge et al.⁵³. The amount of nitrite was determined with a Merck Spectroquant 114773 test kit (Merck KGaA), and NH₃ was analyzed by means of the Nessler method.⁵⁴

Catalytic tests. Catalytic activity was tested in the oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene (EB) using a quartz microreactor filled with 50 mg of a carbon sample placed on a quartz wool. A flow rate of gaseous reactants was controlled by mass flow controllers (Brooks 4800) to obtain a total flow rate of 50 cm³/min (0.4 cm³ of O₂ + 49.6 cm³ of He, O₂:EB molar ratio = 1:1). The EB vapor was introduced into the reaction mixture by passing it through a pure liquid of EB being kept at a constant temperature of 25 °C. The reaction products were transferred directly to a gas chromatograph (Bruker 450-GC) via a six-port valve with heated lines, and there analyzed. The instrument was equipped with three packed columns (Porapak Q, Molecular Sieve 5A, and Chromosorb W-HP) and three detectors (two flame ionization detectors – one coupled with a catalytic methanizer – and a thermal conductivity detector). Prior to a catalytic test, a sample was outgassed in a flow of He (50 cm³/min) at 200 °C for 30 min. The temperature of the catalyst bed was then increased to 350 °C and the dosing of the catalytic mixture began. The first GC analysis was initialized after 15 min. of time-on-stream. The products were analyzed in intervals of 46 min. during the total reaction time of 8 h. The catalytic performance was expressed as conversion of EB (C_{EB}), yield of *i* product (Y_{*i*}) and selectivity towards *i* product (S_{*i*}) using the following equations:

$$C_{EB} = \frac{F_{EB,0} - F_{EB}}{F_{EB,0}} \times 100$$

$$Y_i = \frac{F_i}{F_{EB,0}} \times 100$$

$$S_i = \frac{Y_i}{C_{EB}} \times 100$$

where F_{EB,0} and F_{EB} are the molar flow rates of EB in inlet and outlet streams, whereas F_{*i*} is the molar flow rate of EB being transformed into the *i* product.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structure and texture. To synthesize the parent mesoporous carbon, a commercially available spherical silica gel was used as the hard template, which was modified by a simple impregnation method using an aqueous solution of sucrose as an inexpensive carbon precursor. This facile route led to the obtaining of a carbon replica with a completely preserved spherical shape, as is shown by the SEM images in Figure 1A. Further modifi-

cation of the carbon replica using a HNO_3 solution resulted that numerous and relatively wide craters formed in the spherical particles. With treatment with gaseous NH_3 at elevated temperatures, even deeper pits were observed. The surfaces of the carbon particles were significantly cracked in the case of pre-treatment with HNO_3 (for the sample SK_N). From the point of view of the perfect shape of the catalyst grains, it is obviously unfavorable with the imperfect shapes observed for the sample SK_N, however, these imperfections can be greatly advantageous for the catalytic performance. The cracks can create an additional macrochannel system in the grain volume, opening access to the narrower micro- and mesopores being located in the interior of the particle. Accordingly, the carbonaceous material with a hierarchical porosity is formed.

Table 1. Bulk N content and textural parameters of the pristine and modified mesoporous carbon replicas.

Sample	N content [wt%]	S_{BET} [m^2/g]	V_{micro} [cm^3/g]	V_{meso} [cm^3/g]	V_{total} [cm^3/g]
S0	-	1239	0.01	0.52	1.01
S0_N	0.6	1490	0.04	2.03	2.56
SK	2.0	1205	0.01	1.15	1.51
SK_N	3.2	1415	0.01	1.33	1.80

S0, SK, S0_N, and SK_N stand for unmodified carbon replica, carbon replica treated with HNO_3 , carbon replica treated with NH_3 , and carbon replica treated first with HNO_3 and then NH_3 .

Figure 1. SEM images (A), N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms (B), XRD patterns (C), and Raman spectra (D) collected for the pristine and modified mesoporous carbon replicas. S0, SK, S0_N, and SK_N stand for unmodified carbon replica, carbon replica treated with HNO_3 , carbon replica treated with NH_3 , and carbon replica treated first with HNO_3 and then NH_3 .

The increased accessibility to the pore system was confirmed by the results of low-temperature N_2 adsorption (cf. Fig. 1B and Table 1). The starting material S0 exhibited a type IV isotherm being characteristic of mesoporous solids, and the specific surface area above $1200 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. Nevertheless, further activation of the S0 sample in both the HNO_3 solution and at the NH_3 atmosphere re-

sulted in the opening of wider pores (meso- and macropores), which was manifested by a clear increase in the amount of adsorbed N_2 at high relative pressures p/p_0 . The activated materials were characterized by a very large volume of mesopores and intraparticle voids (even as high as $2.52 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ for S0_N) and expanded S_{BET} (exceeding $1400 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ after the treatment with NH_3).

The structural ordering of the materials was analyzed by XRD (Fig. 1C). The collected XRD patterns show distinct, but rather broad, features at ca. 23° and 43° corresponding to the (002) and (101) reflections typical of a poorly-ordered graphite structure. However, Raman spectroscopy was a more informative way to study features of the carbon structure of the studied materials (Fig. 1D). Two featured bands at 1340 cm⁻¹ and 1590 cm⁻¹ were observed and assigned as the D and G band, respectively. The D band arises from the disordered sp² hybridized carbon, while the G band is associated with crystalline graphitic carbon.⁵⁵ Meanwhile, the intensity ratio of D band and G band (I_D/I_G) is adopted to evaluate the graphitization degree of porous carbon materials.⁵⁶ The I_D/I_G ratios for all N-modified materials were higher than that of S0 (1.11) and the reference reduced graphene oxide (RGO, 0.39), but also higher than the N-doped porous carbon prepared from N-containing zeolitic imidazolate framework with comparable and even higher nitrogen concentration, which has been indicative of that the introduction of defects and disordered structures could be beneficial to applications in catalysis and electrochemistry.^{57,58}

Surface functionalities. The chemical surface compositions of the studied materials were determined by XPS (Table 2). Since carbon, oxygen and nitrogen were the only elements identified, the quantitative analysis was based on the C 1s, O 1s and N 1s regions. The sample treated with NH₃ (S0_N) had 0.7 at.% of nitrogen, and that treated with HNO₃ (SK), 2.6 at.% of nitrogen. Simultaneously, a significant increase in the oxygen content was observed with the HNO₃ treatment, while the NH₃ treatment reduced the oxygen content. The reduced amount of oxygen was linked to the reducing properties of NH₃.⁵⁹

Figure 2. XPS O 1s and N 1s spectra of the pristine and modified mesoporous carbon replicas. S0, SK, S0_N, and SK_N stand for unmodified carbon replica, carbon replica treated with HNO₃, carbon replica treated with NH₃, and carbon replica treated first with HNO₃ and then NH₃.

More detailed results were obtained by deconvolution of the XPS O 1s and N 1s spectra, which provided evidence for several different O and N species being distributed on the carbon-rich surfaces (Fig. 2). In the N 1s core region, four main components at 398.9 eV (± 0.1 eV), 400.2 eV (± 0.1 eV), 401.6 eV (± 0.2 eV) and 405.8 eV (the latter one exceptionally for SK) were distinguished and attributed to pyridinic, pyrrolic, quaternary

nitrogen and oxidized nitrogen species, respectively.^{60,61} In turn, in the O 1s spectra, three essential peaks appeared at 531.1 eV (± 0.1 eV), 532.2 eV (± 0.1 eV) and 533.8 eV (± 0.1 eV) and were assigned to C=O (oxygen atom in carbonyl), O=C-O (oxygen atom in ester, anhydride and carboxylic acid) and C-O (oxygen atom in phenol/ether), respectively.^{62,63} Furthermore, one more component was found at 533.3 eV for the HNO₃ treated sample (SK) and assigned to nitro groups.⁶⁴ Obviously, during the modification of SK with NH₃ (sample SK_N), the nitro species were reduced completely forming mainly pyridinic and pyrrolic functionalities (cf. Table 2). Finally, in the SK_N sample with the highest amount of nitrogen (3.7 at.%), one could also observe significant changes in the distribution of the oxygen species. The performed modification led to the effective elimination of the carboxyl groups, and prevented the relatively high contents of C=O and C-OH moieties observed for the SK material.

To obtain deeper insight into the surface composition of the carbon samples at the atomic level, solid-state NMR experiments were performed. In Figure 3A ¹H MAS NMR spectra (60 kHz MAS) of SK, S0_N, and SK_N are presented. All samples exhibit a very similar pattern of proton signals, where a main, broad resonance (as a consequence of disorder) centered at 8 ppm represents the aromatic protons, and signals in the chemical shift range of 2–4 ppm can be assigned to protons in ethoxy and hydroxyl groups. There is also a signal with a rather unusual negative chemical shift in all three samples, which may be attributable to a so-called nucleus-independent chemical shift (NICS) effect on the protons of H₂O confined in the internal cavities of the doped carbon particles.^{65,66}

Figure 3. ¹H MAS NMR (a) and ¹H-¹³C HETCOR (b) spectra collected from as indicated samples at 60 kHz MAS rate and magnetic field strength 14.1 T. SK, S0_N, and SK_N stand for carbon replica treated with HNO₃, carbon replica treated with NH₃, and carbon replica treated first with HNO₃ and then NH₃.

Table 2. Content of O and N in particular functionalities distributed on the surface of the studied carbon materials.

Sample	Oxygen species [at.%]				Nitrogen species [at.%]					
	C=O	O=C-O	C-O	N-O	total O	pyridinic	pyrrolic	graphitic	oxidized	total N
S0	0.73	1.37	2.44	0.00	4.5	-	-	-	-	-
S0_N	0.51	0.25	1.52	0.00	2.3	0.27	0.22	0.18	0.00	0.7
SK	3.01	4.32	2.49	3.54	13.4	0.17	0.53	0.09	1.81	2.6
SK_N	2.06	0.41	3.16	0.00	5.6	2.40	1.02	0.28	0.00	3.7

S0, SK, S0_N, and SK_N stand for unmodified carbon replica, carbon replica treated with HNO₃, carbon replica treated with NH₃, and carbon replica treated first with HNO₃ and then NH₃.

Figure 4. Directly-excited ^{13}C (a) and ^{15}N (b) MAS NMR spectra of the SK_N sample collected at 7 kHz MAS and 14.1 T, shown together with chemical shifts calculated for hypothetical structural motifs. Experimental chemical shifts are given in black, calculated ^{13}C shifts are in red, and ^{15}N are in blue. All shifts are in ppm. SK_N stands for the carbon replica treated first with HNO₃ and then NH₃.

As revealed by the ^1H - ^{13}C heteronuclear correlation (HETCOR) spectrum of the SK_N sample (Fig. 3B), the broad signal due to the aromatic protons correlates with the ^{13}C resonance of graphitic carbons at ~ 130 ppm, indicating that these protons terminate the edges of the doped carbon. Note that under these experimental conditions of 60 kHz MAS, both the chemical shift anisotropy (CSA) and dipolar resonance broadening are largely suppressed, and so neither contributes significantly to the ^{13}C line width; this line width can therefore be attributed solely to a chemical shifts distribution due to structural disorder. To observe the full range of ^{13}C and ^{15}N environments, direct excitation of a larger sample volume at 7 kHz MAS was also employed. In the directly-excited ^{13}C MAS NMR spectrum of the SK_N sample (Fig. 4A), the resonance of the sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms appears as a spinning sideband manifold with an isotropic chemical shift of 128 ppm and a CSA of -113 ppm. In addition, we also see two minor signals at 63 ppm and 22 ppm. The very narrow line widths of these indicate fast dynamics and therefore we attribute them to the mobile ethoxy groups linked to carbon sheet via ether or ester groups, which is consistent with ^1H proton resonances in the range of 2-4 ppm (Fig. 3A). Similar ^{13}C NMR shifts have been reported for graphite and graphene related materials.⁶⁷⁻⁷⁰

The ^{15}N MAS NMR spectrum of the same sample is presented in Figure 4B. Since no cross-polarization (CP) was used all nitrogen moieties present in the structure should be detectable. Two distinct ^{15}N resonances are clearly identified: one at -74 ppm and another one at -258 ppm. These values fall in the shifts ranges characteristic for pyridinic (-50 to -150 ppm) and pyrrolic (-200 to -270 ppm) nitrogen sites.⁷¹

To corroborate the NMR signal assignments and derive molecular representations of the local motifs present in the material, ^{13}C and ^{15}N NMR chemical shifts were calculated using quantum chemistry methods on a variety of structural models. The perturbatively-corrected DSD-PBEP86 DFT approximation coupled with NMR-optimized pcS- n basis sets currently constitutes the most reliable and robust way for NMR shifts prediction of main group elements.^{51,72} The calculated ^{13}C isotropic chemical shift and CSA for the carbon atom (circled in red) in the graphene model of Figure 4A are in excellent agreement with the values obtained from the experimental spectrum of the SK_N sample. Therefore, it can

be concluded that this local environment represents the majority of the carbon atoms in the sample with spectral broadening originating from structural disorder, and that packing/ π - π stacking effects (if present) are minor, which is also corroborated by not affected shifts of aromatic and ethoxy/hydroxyl protons. Several local environments of nitrogen atoms have been proposed and discussed in the literature on N-doped carbon materials.^{37,73} We considered them herein by construction and evaluation of appropriate models, which are presented in Figure 4B. The only models that exhibit ^{15}N shifts that match the experimental spectrum are those with “pyridinic” nitrogen, and “pyrrolic” nitrogen, in agreement with XPS. The sharp experimental peak at -74 ppm is consistent with only one structural model, which is that of pyridinic nitrogen sited at the edge of the carbon sheet (with a calculated shift of -75 ppm); hence we consider this resonance to represent only this type of pyridinic nitrogen. On the other hand, the interpretation of the broader resonance at -258 ppm requires more care, as it is consistent with three structural models of pyrrolic nitrogen with calculated shifts in the range -254 to -269 ppm: ‘external pyrrolic nitrogen’ (-261 ppm), ‘edge pyrrolic nitrogen’ (-269 ppm), and pyrrolic nitrogen two bonds two bonds from pyridinic nitrogen (-254 and -109 ppm respectively). Fortunately, some simplification in the assignment is possible. The presence of pyrrolic nitrogen two bonds from pyridinic nitrogen can be excluded due to the absence of a resonance close to -109 ppm, and the ‘edge pyrrolic nitrogen’ can also be discounted due to the large mechanical strain required for a five-membered aromatic ring to form at the edge of the carbon sheet. Therefore, we ascribe this resonance solely to ‘external’ pyrrolic nitrogen. The solid-state NMR results also exclude the presence of oxidized nitrogen, as no resonances are observed at -31 ppm ($\text{N}=\text{O}$) or -47 ppm (NO_2), again in agreement with XPS.

These results indicate that the nitrogen atoms are predominantly present at the carbon edges in the carbon replica treated first with HNO_3 and then NH_3 . However, some comment is required to address the absence of any signals in the solid-state NMR spectrum corresponding to graphitic nitrogen, which appears to contradict the XPS results which indicates that graphitic nitrogen is indeed present, albeit in lower amounts. This apparent contradiction can be resolved by the following observations. Firstly, we note that the predicted graphitic nitrogen chemical shifts depend strongly on the distance of the nitrogen from the edge, which would result in a broad resonance. Secondly, the low graphitic content ($\sim 25\%$ compared to pyrrolic nitrogen) would result in inherently low sensitivity for this environment. Both observations indicate that the signals from such graphitic nitrogen environments, if present, are lost within the spectral noise due to the low signal-to-noise ratio of the experimental spectrum as a consequence of direct ^{15}N NMR detection at natural abundance.⁷⁴ Finally, we also note that none of the models with two nitrogens in close proximity (i.e. two/three bonds separation) gives a pair of shifts consistent with the experimental spectrum; therefore we can discount any significant clustering of the nitrogen on doping.

Electrochemical removal of nitrates. The selective doping of carbon materials with nitrogen atoms, i.e. the atomic control over the nitrogen distribution, is of high

importance to tailor the electrocatalytic properties for several electrochemical reactions, such as the ORR or CO_2 reduction.^{75,76} For instance, pyridinic N is considered as the most active catalytic site in comparison to the pyrrolic or graphitic nitrogens for ORR.⁷⁷ Given the atomic resolution of the nitrogen positions within our carbon materials on the basis of ^{15}N solid state NMR experiments, we investigated the electrochemical reduction of nitrate on the nitrogen-free S0 carbon electrode and the SK_N carbon material containing nitrogen at the edge sites. In particular, we were interested in how the presence of nitrogen at these positions affected the selectivity of nitrate reduction toward either molecular nitrogen or NH_3 .

Figure 5. LSV curves of C and edge-N-C in $0.1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ with the absence and presence of 200 ppm nitrate at a scan rate of 1 mV s^{-1} . Current densities relate to geometric current densities. S0 and SK_N stand for unmodified carbon replica and carbon replica treated first with HNO_3 and then NH_3 .

Both the S0 and SK_N carbon-rich electrodes developed cathodic currents due to the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and showed a decrease in geometric current density when no nitrate was added to the solutions. This could be deduced from the linear square voltammetry (LSV) performed under near-neutral conditions for the S0 and SK_N electrodes in the absence and presence of nitrate, depicted in Figure 5. In the presence of nitrate, cathodic peaks are visible at -0.9 V vs. RHE and -0.8 V vs. RHE for both S0 and SK_N electrode. This trend is visible also in the chronoamperometry (CA) recorded at -0.84 V vs. RHE (Fig. 6). Since the electrode preparation was identical for S0 and SK_N, the almost identical current density of -4 mA cm^{-2} at this potential value suggests no relevant influence of the (i) nitrogen positions within the carbon structure, or (ii) the general presence of nitrogen in the carbon samples on the electrochemical activity. This was deduced from the trends in the chronoamperometry (CA) recorded at -0.84 V vs. RHE (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Constant potential electrolysis of C and edge-N-C at -0.84 V vs RHE in 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 with the absence and presence of 200 ppm nitrate. Current densities relate to geometric current densities. S0 and SK_N stand for unmodified carbon replica and carbon replica treated first with HNO_3 and then NH_3 , respectively.

Table 3. Electrochemical reduction of nitrate on S0 and SK_N electrodes in 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 electrolyte.

Electrode	CA conditions	Initial concentration of NO_3^- (ppm)	Final concentration of NO_3^- (ppm)	Reduction efficiency of NO_3^- (%)	Final concentration of NO_2^- (ppm)	Final concentration of NH_4^+ (ppm)	$\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^- + \text{NH}_4^+$ (ppm)
S0	-0.843 V vs RHE for 3 h (pH 5.93)	200	105	47.5	5.8	11.0	121.8
SK_N	-0.843 V vs RHE for 3 h (pH 5.85)	200	103	48.5	8.4	9.7	121.1

S0 and SK_N stand for unmodified carbon replica and carbon replica treated first with HNO_3 and then NH_3 .

To elucidate whether the generated electric current was used to reduce nitrate, we analyzed the nitrate, nitrite and NH_3 concentration after the 3 h of CA at this potential nitrite and NH_3 production (Table 3). The current density for nitrate reduction at -0.84 V vs RHE was almost identical for the bare carbon electrode (S0) and the electrode containing nitrogen atoms as dopants (SK_N). In combination with the structural analysis based on ^{15}N solid-state NMR, the electrochemical results showed that the nitrate reduction was independent of the presence and structural positions of the nitrogen atoms in the carbon material. Furthermore, the nitrogen doping did not influence the outcome of the observed selectivity. It should be noted that this effect may be changed for different electrochemical reactions, such as the nitrogen reduction reaction (NRR) or CO_2 reduction. However, these electrochemical results shed light on the reaction mechanism of nitrate reduction by proving that the selectivity did not depend on the presence of nitrogen atoms.

Oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene. The synthesized carbon materials were also tested in the oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene to determine an influence of the introduction of N into the edge positions on their catalytic activity. We decided to choose this pathway of transformation of EB into styrene, despite the fact that many recent reports have referred to the use of nitrogen-doped carbon materials in the direct dehydrogenation of EB.^{24,62,63,78,79} The oxidative route allows to significantly reduce the process temperature and omit the thermodynamic limitations, and thus leads to greater economic opportunities to implement the developed technology.⁸⁰⁻⁸²

Table 4. Conversion of EB and selectivity to styrene achieved in the oxidative dehydrogenation of EB at 350 °C over the studied catalysts at the beginning (15 min. time-on-stream) and the end of catalytic run (360 min. time-on-stream).

Catalyst	EB conversion [%]		Selectivity to styrene [%]	
	15 min.	360 min.	15 min.	360 min.
S0	29.8	17.2	95.1	94.2
S0_N	33.4	16.2	98.0	96.8
SK	34.0	14.1	96.1	96.0
SK_N	38.7	19.2	96.3	96.6

S0, SK, S0_N, and SK_N stand for unmodified carbon replica, carbon replica treated with HNO_3 , carbon replica treated with NH_3 , and carbon replica treated first with HNO_3 and then NH_3 .

The studied carbon materials appeared to be very active and selective at a chosen temperature of 350 °C (Table 4). Apart from styrene ($>94\%$), only small amounts of by-products (mainly CO_2) were formed. Evidently, the initial catalytic activity and selectivity to the desired product increased on N doping. However, the best results were achieved over SK_N, which gave after 15 min time-on-stream an EB conversion as high as 38.7% with a selectivity towards styrene of 96.3% . During the catalytic runs all studied catalysts lost gradually their initial activity due to coke deposition, which is a typical side reaction observed in the dehydrogenation of alkanes even under an oxidizing atmosphere. Nevertheless, the SK_N catalyst

still showed 19.2% of the EB conversion after 6 h of the reaction with the selectivity to styrene (96.6%) close to the initial value.

The catalytic role of the N-containing groups in the oxidative dehydrogenation of alkanes was attributed to activation of the O₂ molecule, which is suggested to be most efficient at graphitic nitrogen sites.^{61,83} The calculations showed that a difference in electronegativity causes a transfer of electrons from C atoms to graphitic N atoms obtaining a positive charge and becoming adsorption sites for oxygen molecules. On the other hand, it was found that N doping facilitates C–H breaking in an alkane molecule and desorption of a resulting alkene molecule.⁸⁴ Nevertheless, Pelech et al.⁸⁵ did not observe any correlation between a content of quaternary nitrogen in N-doped carbon xerogels and their catalytic activity in the oxidative dehydrogenation of isobutene. A clear relationship was found for the total nitrogen content. Our study based on the application of ¹⁵N solid-state NMR and XPS clarifies this finding. The catalytic effect of N species in the oxidative dehydrogenation processes should rather correspond to their presence at the edge sites. However, it should be kept in mind that other factors also determine the catalytic activity of these materials. In our case, the modification procedure resulted in a partial destruction of perfect spherical morphology, giving a higher porosity (including an expanded surface area) and accessibility of reacting molecules to the active sites. However, the influence of these morphological changes are difficult to assess and differentiate from those related to the N-doping at the current state. Additionally, high disorder of the carbon structure (confirmed by Raman spectroscopy) and significant elimination of COOH groups combined with exposition of catalytically active C=O/C–O ones (revealed by XPS) could potentially have a beneficial effect for the catalytic performance.

CONCLUSION

¹⁵N solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy was proven to be an excellent tool to recognize the type of N species being generated on the surface of a mesoporous carbon replica. Furthermore, theoretical considerations showed the detailed location of the N atoms in the carbon structure. For the material synthesized by nanoreplication of a silica template using sucrose as a carbon source, modification based on a contact with HNO₃ solution followed by a treatment in gaseous NH₃ at elevated temperature appeared to be the most efficient way to form a high amount of pyridinic N at the edge and pyrrolic N external to the edge. The presence of these moieties did not influence significantly the electrochemical activity in NO₃⁻ elimination, but was important for the observed improved catalytic performance in the oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene for the N-rich carbon catalysts. The developed N-loaded carbon catalyst with spherical morphology (confirmed by SEM), expanded mesopore system (N₂ adsorption), suitable graphitization (XRD, Raman spectroscopy) and tuned C=O/C–OH distribution on the surface (XPS), produced by using the simple and inexpensive procedure, could be a relevant candidate for further studies towards commercial applications.

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